

Supplemental Materials

A Systematic Benchmark of Cross-Material Transfer Learning for Concrete Compressive Strength Prediction

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This supplemental document provides additional tables and figures that support the manuscript titled “A Systematic Benchmark of Cross-Material Transfer Learning for Concrete Compressive Strength Prediction.” These materials include literature summary tables, dataset statistics, metric definitions, hyperparameter settings, extended target-data-size results, and representative hyperparameter tuning figures.

S1. Literature Summary Tables

Tables S1 and S2 provide supporting literature summaries for the Introduction. Table S1 summarizes representative machine-learning studies related to concrete compressive strength prediction, including the concrete type, input variables, modeling methods, and dataset size. Table S2 summarizes representative transfer-learning studies in concrete, cement-based materials, structural behavior prediction, corrosion prediction, and image-based damage detection. These tables provide background context for the research gap discussed in the main manuscript.

Table S1: Summary of some studies on ML applications for predicting concrete CS

Study	Concrete type	Input variables	ML methods evaluated	Dataset size
Liu et al. (2026)	Limestone manufactured sand concrete	SP _r , W/C, S _r , W, CA, S	XGBoost, KNN, RF, SVR, CatBoost, ANN	307

Tan et al. (2026)	Rubberized concrete	W/C, R, S _R , C, FAC, CA, SF/C, SP, A	ANN, SVR, RF, ERT, XGBoost, LightGBM	1209
Jamal and Ahmed (2025)	High-performance concrete (HPC)	OPC, GGBS, SF, W, SP, FAC, CA, MC-FA, MC-CA, A	LR, DT, SVR, ET, GPR, ANN	152
Dabiri et al. (2022)	RAC	OPC, W/C, CA, FAC, RCA, RFA, S, SP/C, A	LR, NR, RF, ANN (GA/SSA/GOA), M5P	234
Pallapothu et al. (2023)	Normal Concrete	W/B, B, %CA, %FA, PD	LR, RF, DT, XGBoost, SVR	479
Dao et al. (2019)	GPC incorporating steel-slag aggregates	FA, Na ₂ SiO ₃ , NaOH, W	ANN, ANFIS	210
Al-Shamiri et al. (2019)	HSC	W, C, FAC, CA, SP	ELM, ANN	324
DeRousseau et al. (2019)	Field-placed concrete	C, FA, W, WRA, CA, FAC, Air	LR, PR, SVR, GPR, RT, RF, BT	Field (1681), Laboratory (311)
Li et al. (2024)	Ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC)	C, SF, S, FA, LP, NS, W/B, QP, S, Fi, SP, Ag	RF, SVR, KNN (optimized with PSO, BAS, SO)	727

Variables: SP_r → Stone powder replacement ratio; W/C → Water–cement ratio; S_r → Sand ratio; W → Water content; CA → Coarse aggregate content; S → Sand content; R → Rubber content; S_R → Maximum size of crumb rubber; C → Cement content; FAC → Fine aggregate content; SF/C → Silica fume–cement ratio; SP → Superplasticizer; A → Age of testing; OPC → Ordinary Portland Cement content; BFS → Blast furnace slag; SF → Silica fume content; MC-FA → Fine aggregate moisture content; MC-CA → Coarse aggregate moisture content; RCA → Recycled coarse aggregate; RFA → Recycled fine aggregate; SP/C → Superplasticizer–cement ratio; W/B → Water–binder ratio; B → Binder content; PD → Packing density; FA → Fly ash content; Na₂SiO₃ → Sodium Silicate; NaOH → Sodium Hydroxide; WRA → Water-reducing admixture; LP → Limestone powder; NS → Nano-silica; QP → Quartz Powder; Fi → Filler; Ag → Aggregate

ML methods: XGBoost → eXtreme Gradient Boosting; KNN → K-Nearest Neighbors; RF → Random Forest; SVR → Support Vector Regressor; CatBoost → Categorical Boosting; ANN → Artificial Neural Network; ERT → Extremely Randomized Trees; LightGBM → Light Gradient-Boosting Machine; LR → Linear Regression; DT → Decision Tree; ET → Ensembles of trees; GPR → Gaussian Process Regression; NR → Nonlinear regression; GA → Genetic Algorithm; SSA → Salp Swarm Algorithm; GOA → Grasshopper Optimization Algorithm; M5P → M5 Prime; ANFIS → Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System; ELM → Extreme Learning Machine; PR → Polynomial regression; BT → Boosted Trees; PSO → Particle Swarm Optimization; BAS → Beetle Antennae Search; SO → Snake Optimization

Table S2: Summary of TL applications in concrete-related problems

Study	TL Method	T^S	T^T	Dataset Size (S/T)
Pak and Paal (2022)	Instance-based	RC column strength (varied domains)	RC column strength (limited data)	497 total (varied splits)
Ji et al. (2024)	Hybrid (feature + instance)	Corrosion (lab mortar)	Corrosion (field concrete)	240 / 81
Gardner et al. (2020)	Feature-based (ANN)	CS (conventional concrete)	CS (specialized concrete)	~1000+ / small
Pak et al. (2023)	Hybrid (ensemble TL)	Shear (slender beams)	Shear (deep beams)	1244 / 605

Su and Wang (2020)	Feature-based (CNN)	ImageNet	Crack detection	large / 12k
Dunphy et al. (2022)	GAN-based TL	Concrete images (unlabeled)	Damage classification	~56k / subset
Iraniparast et al. (2023)	Fine-tuned CNN	ImageNet	Crack detection	large / ~4k
Ford et al. (2022)	Parameter-based (ANN)	f _c / E prediction	Cross-property / dataset	~1030, 526 / ~228, 104
Nguyen et al. (2025)	Feature-based	CS prediction	CS (new conditions)	~1000+ / few hundred

CS → Compressive Strength; RC → Reinforced Concrete; CNN → Convolutional Neural Network; GAN → Generative Adversarial Network; f_c → Concrete compressive strength; E → Elastic Modulus; S/T → Source/Target; ImageNet → Large-Scale Visual Database for Image Recognition.

S2. Dataset Statistics

Table S3 provides the descriptive statistics for the source and target datasets used in this study. The table reports the range, central tendency, dispersion, and skewness of the input and output variables before model training. These statistics support the discussion of source–target differences and domain shift in the main manuscript.

Table S3: Statistical summary of all datasets

Dataset	Variable	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Mode	Median	SD	Skewness
S	C	93.0	708.33	307.95	425.00	298.00	122.19	0.57
	BFS	0.0	359.40	49.91	0.00	0.00	78.89	1.38
	FA	0.0	319.00	65.23	0.00	35.56	75.45	0.88
	W	121.8	247.00	180.94	192.00	180.31	23.75	0.20
	W/B	0.2	0.90	0.45	0.40	0.45	0.13	0.28
	SP	0.00	36.50	6.29	0.00	5.72	6.32	1.23
	FAR	0.3	0.57	0.44	0.39	0.43	0.05	0.22
	A	1.0	365.00	42.74	28.00	28.00	56.44	3.44
	CS	1.1	123.00	41.59	42.00	38.22	23.79	0.93
T ₁	C	140.0	600.00	356.00	350.00	361.00	72.76	-0.88
	SF	0.00	50.00	1.09	0.00	0.00	6.14	6.08
	FA	0.00	227.50	27.29	0.00	0.00	58.10	1.98
	W	120.0	271.00	193.32	205.00	193.10	26.02	-0.32
	NFA	0.00	1065.0	650.11	642.00	685.00	222.31	-1.42
	NCA	0.00	1366.0	529.91	0.00	543.20	447.36	-0.03
	RFA	0.00	1000.0	32.98	0.00	0.00	134.79	4.53
	RCA	0.00	1632.0	518.49	0.00	496.50	427.87	0.27
	A	1.00	180.00	32.66	28.00	28.00	36.43	2.07
T ₂	CS	5.96	121.42	41.50	27.54	39.79	18.66	1.01
	BFS	0.00	488.00	218.65	0.00	228.00	153.90	0.12
	CCA	0.00	488.00	215.24	0.00	195.00	152.78	0.13
	FAC	728.00	899.00	818.12	841.00	841.00	56.90	-0.14

T ₃	CA	1044.0	1045.0	1045.0	1045.0	1045.0	0.09	-
	W	32.64	37.86	35.22	37.86	35.16	2.15	0.04
	SHP	20.74	25.96	23.38	20.74	23.44	2.15	-0.04
	SSG	146.30	146.40	146.40	146.40	146.40	0.01	-
	A	7.00	90.00	45.25	7.00	42.00	31.20	0.25
	MC	12.00	16.00	14.00	12.00	14.00	1.65	0.00
	CS	10.67	64.09	35.90	29.04	36.04	12.19	0.17
	C	408.0	659.0	517.7	434.0	513.5	63.77	0.36
	SF	0.0	59.0	24.9	0.0	23.5	18.23	0.13
	W	160.0	168.0	164.7	166.0	165.0	2.12	-0.46
	SP	6.7	14.5	9.3	8.1	8.6	1.95	0.88
	CA	1105.0	1173.0	1136.2	1114.0	1130.0	21.43	0.21
	FAC	488.0	700.0	602.5	618.0	609.0	59.12	-0.25
	A	1.0	56.0	19.0	1.0	7.0	20.90	0.88
T ₄	CS	21.2	113.7	67.0	63.1	67.9	23.50	-0.16
	W	160.00	180.00	170.00	160.00	170.00	8.18	0.00
	C	284.00	600.00	417.81	360.00	411.00	77.03	0.41
	CA	552.00	951.00	767.71	731.00	769.50	85.45	-0.19
	FAC	845.00	989.00	898.51	845.00	898.00	43.82	0.02
	SP	0.00	2.00	0.95	1.00	1.00	0.55	0.02
	CS	37.50	73.60	51.93	41.50	48.90	9.45	0.44

C → Cement content; BFS → blast furnace slag; FA → fly ash content; W → water content; W/B → water-to-binder ratio; SP → superplasticizer dosage; FAR → fine aggregate ratio, A → age of testing; CS → compressive strength; SF → Silica Fume; NFA → Natural Fine Aggregates (NFA); NCA → Natural Coarse Aggregates; RFA → Recycled Fine Aggregates; RCA → Recycled Coarse Aggregates; CCA → corncob ash; SHP → sodium hydroxide pellets; SSG → sodium silicate gel; MC → molarity concentration; CA → coarse aggregate content; FAC → fine aggregate content. W/B and FAR are unitless; A, MC, and CS are reported in days, M, and MPa, respectively; all other variables are reported in kg/m³.

S3. Evaluation Metrics

Table S4 provides the definitions and interpretation of the regression metrics used for model evaluation. Root mean squared error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and coefficient of determination R² were used to evaluate predictive accuracy and model fit. These metrics were used consistently for hyperparameter tuning, final test-set evaluation, and comparison of transfer-learning strategies.

Table S4: Formulas and guidance for the evaluation metrics used in this study.

Metric	Equation	Guidance
RMSE	$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y_i^p)^2}$	Lower RMSE values reflect better accuracy; the metric penalizes large errors more strongly, providing insight into worst-case deviations.

MAE	$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i - y_i^p $	Smaller MAE values imply that, on average, the model’s predictions deviate only slightly from actual observations.
R ²	$1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y_i^p)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$	Values approaching 1 indicate that the model captures most of the variability in the data and provides a strong overall fit.

S4. Hyperparameter Settings and Tuning Results

Tables S5 and S6 summarize the final selected hyperparameters for the fine-tuning-based and feature-extraction-based transfer-learning models, respectively. The selected hyperparameters were obtained using cross-validation on the corresponding training data, while the independent target test sets were reserved for final evaluation.

Table S5: Final selected hyperparameters for models in fine-tuning-based TL method

Target data	Phase	LR	BS	L2 Reg.	Epochs
T ₁	Source	0.005	64	0.01	500
	Phase 1	0.001	8	0.001	1000
	Phase 2	0.001	16	0.001	900
	Phase 3	0.001	8	0.001	650
	Phase 4	10 ⁻⁶	64	0.0	200
	Baseline	0.05	64	0.001	500
T ₂	Source	0.005	64	0.001	700
	Phase 1	0.05	16	0.0	700
	Phase 2	0.001	32	0.001	700
	Phase 3	0.001	32	0.0	700
	Phase 4	5×10 ⁻⁶	8	0.001	100
	Baseline	0.01	64	0.0	500
T ₃	Source	0.01	128	0.01	500
	Phase 1	0.001	8	0.0	500
	Phase 2	0.001	32	0.001	500
	Phase 3	5×10 ⁻⁴	32	10 ⁻⁵	200
	Phase 4	10 ⁻⁴	16	10 ⁻⁵	50
	Baseline	0.05	64	0.001	700
T ₄	Source	0.001	256	10 ⁻⁴	300
	Phase 1	0.05	8	0.001	300
	Phase 2	0.01	16	0.001	500
	Phase 3	0.001	8	0.001	700
	Phase 4	10 ⁻⁴	16	0.001	300
	Baseline	0.001	64	0.01	300

Table S6: Final selected hyperparameters for models in feature-extraction-based TL method

Model	Hyperparameter	Training strategy	T₁	T₂	T₃	T₄
RF	max_depth	TL	20	10	10	5
		Baseline	None	10	10	None
	max_features	TL	0.5	1.0	1.0	1.0
		Baseline	0.5	0.75	0.75	1.0
	min_samples_leaf	TL	0.1	1	2	4
		Baseline	1	1	2	1
XGBoost	n_estimators	TL	300	500	300	800
		Baseline	800	500	300	100
	learning_rate	TL	0.03	0.05	0.1	0.005
		Baseline	0.1	0.03	0.1	0.1
	max_depth	TL	5	3	2	4
		Baseline	5	4	2	3
n_estimators	TL	500	800	300	800	
	Baseline	800	800	800	800	
subsample	TL	0.8	1.0	0.8	0.6	
	Baseline	0.6	0.8	0.6	0.8	

Figs. S1–S3 provide representative hyperparameter tuning results. Fig. S1 shows the source-model tuning surfaces for the four target-transfer cases. Fig. S2 shows representative fine-tuning tuning surfaces for T₁. Fig. S3 shows feature-extraction tuning heatmaps for T₁ using RF and XGBoost. These figures document the tuning process used to select model configurations reported in the main manuscript.

Fig. S1. Source model hyperparameter tuning surfaces for the target-transfer cases: (a,b) T₁, (c,d) T₂, (e,f) T₃, and (g,h) T₄.

Fig. S2. Representative fine-tuning hyperparameter tuning surfaces for T_1 : (a,b) Phase 1 output-layer fine-tuning and (c,d) Phase 4 full-network fine-tuning.

Fig. S3. Hyperparameter tuning heatmaps for T_1 using direct source-trained feature extraction without fine-tuning: (a,b) RF tuning and (c,d) XGBoost tuning.

S5. Target-Data-Size Sensitivity Results

Tables S7 and S8 provide the detailed numerical results for the target-data-size sensitivity analysis. Table S7 reports the mean test-set performance of Phase 3 fine-tuned transfer-learning models trained using different fractions of the available target training data. Table S8 reports the corresponding standard deviations across repeated runs. These results support the discussion in the main manuscript on how target-data availability affects accuracy and robustness.

Table S7: Mean test-set performance of Phase 3 fine-tuned TL models trained using different percentages of the available target training data across the target datasets

Target data	5%		10%		25%		50%		100%	
	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2	RMSE	R^2
T_1	17.12	0.221	16.27	0.298	12.32	0.595	8.86	0.791	7.82	0.837
T_2	6.45	0.702	5.40	0.787	4.21	0.864	2.38	0.959	1.99	0.972
T_3	13.86	0.692	13.02	0.728	9.48	0.853	7.58	0.906	6.16	0.939
T_4	8.22	0.052	6.13	0.478	4.71	0.691	4.43	0.727	3.81	0.796

Table S8: Standard deviation of test-set performance of Phase 3 fine-tuned TL models trained using different percentages of the available target training data across repeated runs and target datasets

Target data	5%		10%		25%		50%		100%	
	RMSE	R ²								
T ₁	0.974	0.087	0.484	0.04	1.15	0.077	0.787	0.037	0.769	0.032
T ₂	0.589	0.053	1.08	0.080	1.38	0.078	0.317	0.011	0.086	0.002
T ₃	1.62	0.070	1.79	0.074	1.94	0.055	1.70	0.043	0.71	0.014
T ₄	1.01	0.223	0.246	0.042	0.330	0.043	0.246	0.030	0.539	0.059

References

- Dabiri, H., Kioumars, M., Kheyroddin, A., Kandiri, A., and Sartipi, F. (2022). “Compressive strength of concrete with recycled aggregate; a machine learning-based evaluation.” *Cleaner Mater.*, 3, 100044. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clema.2022.100044>.
- DeRousseau, M. A., Laftchiev, E., Kasprzyk, J. R., Rajagopalan, B., and Srubar, W. V. (2019). “A comparison of machine learning methods for predicting the compressive strength of field-placed concrete.” *Constr. Build. Mater.*, 228, 116661. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.08.042>.
- Dunphy, K., Sadhu, A., and Wang, J. (2022). “Multiclass damage detection in concrete structures using a transfer learning-based generative adversarial networks.” *Struct. Control Health Monit.*, 29(11). <https://doi.org/10.1002/stc.3079>.
- Ford, E., Maneparambil, K., Kumar, A., Sant, G., and Neithalath, N. (2022). “Transfer (machine) learning approaches coupled with target data augmentation to predict the mechanical properties of concrete.” *Mach. Learn. Appl.*, 8, 100271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mlwa.2022.100271>.
- Iraniparast, M., Ranjbar, S., Rahai, M., and Moghadas Nejad, F. (2023). “Surface concrete cracks detection and segmentation using transfer learning and multi-resolution image processing.” *Structures*, 54, 386–398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2023.05.062>.
- Jamal, A. S., and Ahmed, A. N. (2025). “Estimating compressive strength of high-performance concrete using different machine learning approaches.” *Alexandria Eng. J.*, 114, 256–265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2024.11.084>.

Ji, H., Tian, Y., Fu, C., and Ye, H. (2024). “Transfer learning enables prediction of steel corrosion in concrete under natural environments.” *Cem. Concr. Compos.*, 148, 105488.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2024.105488>.

Li, Y., Yang, X., Ren, C., Wang, L., and Ning, X. (2024). “Predicting the compressive strength of ultra-high-performance concrete based on machine learning optimized by meta-heuristic algorithm.” *Buildings*, 14(5), 1209. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings14051209>.

Liu, Z., Xie, K., Ge, B., and Zhu, M. (2026). “Prediction and interpretability of compressive strength in limestone manufactured sand concrete using machine learning and microstructural analysis.” *J. Build. Eng.*, 120, 115562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2026.115562>.

Nguyen, H. A. T., Pham, D. H., Le, A. T., Ahn, Y., Oo, B. L., and Lim, B. T. H. (2025). “Transfer learning framework for modelling the compressive strength of ultra-high performance geopolymer concrete.” *Constr. Build. Mater.*, 459, 139746. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2024.139746>.

Pak, H., Leach, S., Yoon, S. H., and Paal, S. G. (2023). “A knowledge transfer enhanced ensemble approach to predict the shear capacity of reinforced concrete deep beams without stirrups.” *Comput.-Aided Civ. Infrastruct. Eng.*, 38(11), 1520–1535. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mice.12965>.

Su, C., and Wang, W. (2020). “Concrete cracks detection using convolutional neural network based on transfer learning.” *Math. Probl. Eng.*, 2020, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/7240129>.

Tan, X., Xing, J., Wang, Y., Qiu, H., Mahjoubi, S., and Guo, P. (2026). “Explainable machine learning for predicting compressive strength of rubberized concrete: SHAP interpretation, lifecycle assessment, and design recommendations.” *J. Cleaner Prod.*, 538, 147338.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.147338>.